

IMPACT OF ETHICAL LEADERSHIP TYPES ON SERVICE SABOTAGE BEHAVIOR, MEDIATOR ROLE OF ETHICAL CLIMATE; A CASE STUDY OF PAKISTAN EDUCATION INSTITUTE

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ABSTRACT

The main aim of study is to assess the effect of ethical leadership three types i.e., (1) Leader Human Orientation, (2) Leader Responsibility Orientation, and (3) Leader Justice Orientation on Service Sabotage Behaviour, Mediator role of ethical climate. Study motivated with Pakistan education institute employee's ethical standard. Study used 313 participant education institute employees' data and applied descriptive, correlation, regression and robustness test for estimation. Result of study indicated Leader Human Orientation and Leader Responsibility Orientation are 1% highly significant impact on service sabotage behaviour. Meanwhile Leader Justice Orientation is 10% significant impact on service sabotage behaviour, therefore, mediator Inverse influencing impact on ethical leadership types, when mediator applied Leader Justice Orientation influence role increase and Leader Human Orientation and Leader Responsibility Orientation influence role reduced. Robustness indicated all variable are highly important for education sector due to employee's behaviour, and for quality of work. Ethical principles not established in education institute a solid route cause for employee's service sabotage behaviours. Educational Employee's behaviour highly important for institution, quality of work maintains through employees efficient behaviour and ethical leadership role enhance when education institute implement ethics and avoid behaviour reactions, therefore ethical leader must focus on employee's behaviour to avoid service sabotage behaviour.

Keywords: Ethical Leadership, Service Sabotage Behavior, Ethical Climate, Pakistan

INTRODUCTION

Recent Review of literature of ethical leader and climate includes managerial decision- making, business ethics, and applied psychology of service employees. Understanding ethical issues in organization empirical literature mostly based on theoretical (Murphy, Smith et al. 1992, Tyson 1992, Ford and Richardson 1994). Several authors indicated need of quality of ethics in business (Randall and Gibson 1990, Ford and Richardson 1994). Some researches identify various ethical

leader types (Robertson 1993, Dierkes and Zimmerman 1994). Suggested ethical leader may able to maintain ethical environment and avoid service sabotage behavior. Therefore, Researcher presenting evidence a strong links between ethical leader, climate of an organization and service sabotage behavior. Empirical investigations impact of ethical behavior on worker satisfaction and behavior (Vitell and Davis 1990), found less satisfied when unethical behavior was common

within organization lead to service sabotage behavior. Ethical leader, climate and service behavior are three distinct concepts. The ethical climate of organization or institution is defined by share perception of how ethical problem should be addressed and what measure take place for correction of behaviour. Ethical leader implementing and compliance the organizational principle on field, Service sabotage is employee's misconduct during service and intentionally neglecting efficient services (Harris and Ogbonna 2006, Dimitriou and Schwepker Jr 2019). Service sabotage behaviour is more prevalent at educational institution workplaces (Harris and Ogbonna 2002, Harris and Ogbonna 2009, Sulu, Ceylan et al. 2010). Service sabotage behaviour occur when organizational principle against the employees demand and requirement. Infact, for ethical behaviour is important for ethical climate of organization (Sinclair 1993). There are different types of ethical leader within organization (Cullen, Parboteeah et al. 2003), empirical ethical theory (Williams and Collins 1995, Viezzer, Egler et al. 2018), moral development or behaviour development (Kurtines and Greif 1974, Carpendale 2000), organizational social cultural theories (Schneider and Reichers 1983) and developed 36 moral climate descriptions. Behaviour and moral climate description based on different types of criteria I.e. thoughtful principle, Contributory and level of analysis, humanity, individual responsibility and organizational principle and commitment. A factor analysis of behaviour leader descriptions resulted in three ethical leader types Leader Human Orientation, Leader Responsibility Orientation, and Leader Justice Orientation. We will use these ethical leader types to measure the impact of ethical climate on service sabotage behaviour. This study was conducted in Pakistan educational sector where institute have to ignore in ethical climate. This is surprising given the evidence that educational institute have come under a lot of inspection in popular press for unethical and problematic activities (Bagan-Sebastian, Milian-Masanet et al. 1992, Siegel, Hulley et al. 1992). Specifically, study will investigate (a) the organizational ethical leader type and climate (b) service sabotage behaviour in educational sector (C) impact of different organizational ethical leader type and climate on service sabotage behaviour.

ICAL LEADERSHIP

Employee's action in according institute principles conceives ethical leadership. A positive organizational climate to be perceived within educational institution will undeniably contribute to the development of ethical behaviour toward attitudes of educational employees. Infact principles of institute increase the social responsibility, job satisfaction level, and commitment of employees to the institutions and thus increase their trust towards the institute (Dimitriou and Schwepker Jr 2019, Yousef and Shadi 2022). There are several types of ethical leader within institution (Corley and Minick 2002, Cullen, Parboteeah et al. 2003), ethical theory (Williams and Collins 1995), ethical development or behaviour development (Kutnick 1986, Carpendale 2000), institution social cultural theories (Schneider and Reichers 1983) and developed 36 moral climate descriptions. Behaviour and ethical climate report based on different types of principles I.e. thoughtful principle, Contributory and level of analysis, humanity, individual responsibility and institution principle and commitment. A factor analysis of behaviour leader reports caused in three ethical leader types (1) Leader Human Orientation, (2) Leader Responsibility Orientation, and (3) Leader Justice Orientation. We will use these ethical leader types to measure the impact of ethical Leaders on service sabotage behaviour.

SERVICE SABOTAGE BEHAVIOUR

Service sabotage behaviour deliberated employees action toward against service quality and frustration educational service counters (Rahmat and Bastian 2022). Empirical studies view-point about service sabotage and active damage services. Most of researchers reflect service sabotage to engage limiting the services (Taylor and Walton 2020). Moreover, sabotage behaviour typically intention to direct control the services against quality customer. Service sabotage treated customer by worsening their service. Service Sabotage theory distinguished the blunders of employees intentionally harm-service sabotage (Harris and Ogbonna 2009, Fehr, Yam et al. 2015). Sabotage services contain shifting the speed of service due to incongruity personal mood and needs, employee intentionally maltreating with customer and frustration in educational institution the service sabotage. Sabotage behaviour not only obstruction the

services, but also damaged the quality and the customer satisfaction, loyalty and performance (Gremier and Gwinner 2000, Mukhtar, Kazmi et al. 2022). Studies empirically discussed theory keep of resource, which establish grounds for substantial outcome of emotional and service sabotage. According to the COR theory personal aims are respectable and achievement for unbiased in serve. When leader mistreat with employees leads to employees mistreat with customer cause of loss self-esteem and emotional resources, due to employee invest their time, energy and resources to serve customer. In similarly, ethical leader restore employees positive behaviour as harm customers restore with employees positive behaviour (Shao and Skarlicki 2014).

ETHICAL CLIMATE

Ethical leaders able to maintain ethical climate and avoid harm service sabotage behavior. Thus, Researcher presenting evidences strong relationship between ethical leader, institution climate and service sabotage behavior. Empirical inquiries about impact of ethical behavior on education institute employees satisfaction and behavior (Vitell and Davis 1990, Vitell and Davis 1990), found less satisfied when unethical behavior was common within institute lead to service sabotage behavior. Climate distinct concept, the ethical institute climate is defined by share perception of how ethical problem should be addressed and what measure take place for correction of behaviour.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The main purpose of this study is to estimate the effect of ethical leadership three types i.e., (1) Leader Human Orientation, (2) Leader Responsibility Orientation, and (3) Leader Justice Orientation on Service Sabotage Behaviour, Mediator role of ethical climate. This Study focused on Pakistan education institution employee's ethical standard and service sabotage behaviour. Ethical standard and principles not established in education institution a solid route cause provided education institute employee's for service sabotage behaviours. In order employees behaviour principles of education institute must regularized (Altahat and Atan 2018, Enwereuzor 2023). Ethical standard, employee's behaviour and accountability should be in order to create a good working

envir
onment in institution. Ethical leader types to measure the impact of ethical Leaders on service sabotage behaviour. Therefore Service sabotage in education institute employee's action during service and intentionally neglecting quality of services (Harris and Ogbonna 2006, Schwepker, Dimitriou et al. 2019). Service-sabotage behaviour is dominated at education institute (Harris and Ogbonna 2002, Harris and Ogbonna 2009, Sulu, Ceylan et al. 2010).

Teacher's behaviour toward service sabotage also harm the institute credibility and performance, while it's negatively impact on student perception of quality work, mouth behaviour more damage as others. Service sabotage behaviour is more important, when education sector due to service provider speak and actions with students perceived quality of services and engagement (Schneider and Bowen 1992, Arif and Al Hassan 2022). Previous studies topic overlooked in education sectors, therefore only few studies conducted on education institution for sabotage behaviour (Harris and Ogbonna 2012, Ramshida and Manikandan 2013). Previous studies directed single case study after interview, lacking survey in different institutions.

Service sabotage literature displaying shed-light on service-sabotage behaviour (Ogbonna and Harris 2009, Harris and Ogbonna 2012). Purpose the study to expands the literature for educational institution. First aims to present theoretical logic and empirical evidence about education institution; why student gives negative feedback of service. Therefore, physical-mental exhaustion cause by extreme and long stress and increase market-institution competition in education sector more focus on quality service ((Zeithaml, Berry et al. 1996) (Browning 2008). Most institution focus on to control employee's emotion and expressions (Diefendorff and Richard 2003, Harris and Ogbonna 2006). Emotions is significant when employees interactions with students (Ashforth and Humphrey 1993, Shinwari, Iqbal et al. 2023). As a result, teachers were aside their genuine emotion that sake education quality. Unseen emotion may be cause of service sabotage behaviour. An emotional inconsistency differ inner feelings and outer expressions. Therefore actions repeat create emotional pain and reduced teacher performance (Cropanzano, Weiss et al. 2003, Jamil and Rasheed 2023).

When employees contribute lack quality services, emotional aspects is main cause of educational employees behaviour lead to service sabotage(Giardini and Frese 2006, Harris and Ogbonna 2006). Ethical climate and education institute employees were effect on institute performance(Abubakar and Arasli 2016). Thus, ethical climate positive impact on individual employee’s performance (Yeşiltaş and Tuna 2018). The ultimate goal of this study is to provide knowledge about service-sabotage behaviour at education sector employees by applying employee’s emotional labour model.

HYPOTHESIS

- H1: There is a positive relationship between Ethical leadership type Leader Human Orientation and Service Sabotage Behaviour.
- H2: There is a positive relationship between Ethical leadership type Leader Responsibility Orientation and Service Sabotage Behaviour.
- H3: There is a positive relationship between Ethical leadership type Leader Justice Orientation and Service Sabotage Behaviour.
- H4: Mediator role of ethical climate enhance the relationship between Ethical leadership types and Service Sabotage Behaviour.

METHODOLOGY

The main purpose of this study is to estimate the effect of ethical leadership three types i.e., (1) Leader Human Orientation, (2) Leader Responsibility Orientation, and (3) Leader Justice Orientation on Service Sabotage Behaviour, Mediator role of ethical climate. This Study focused on Pakistan education institution employee’s ethical standard and service sabotage behaviour. This study constitute participants from Pakistan Punjab

education institute, the participants were randomly select in education sector of Pakistan. Study communicated approximately 313 education institute employees through various online and forum site. Invitation through what’s up survey questionnaire and those accept invitation participation share survey link for access the survey site. Survey site design according article title, instruction, study aims, and reports of variable questions. Employee’s affiliation, age, sex, and education required in online survey. Analysis variables through realistic models and scale are; 1. Strongly disagree and 5. Strongly agree based. Responses of education institute employees test through reliability test (Nunn ally, 1978), Cranach’s alpha estimate at 0.90 CIT, Flanagan, 1954), descriptive for potential variable, correlation for endogenty, regression for impact estimation and robustness method use for test validity of data and results.

Results and Discussion

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics

Variable Description	Mean	Median	Maximum	Minimum	Std. Dev.	Skewness	Kurtosis
Leader Human Orientation	3.995	4.000	5.000	1.000	0.796	-0.740	3.771
Leader Justice Orientation	3.746	4.000	5.000	1.000	0.967	-0.536	3.099
Leader Responsibility Orientation	3.670	4.000	5.000	1.000	0.974	-0.570	3.160
Ethical Climate	4.207	4.000	5.000	1.000	0.828	-0.952	3.734
Service Sabotage Behaviour	3.674	4.000	5.000	1.000	1.086	-0.646	3.030

Table 1 showing estimate the effect of ethical leadership three types i.e., (1) Leader Human Orientation, (2) Leader Responsibility Orientation, and (3) Leader Justice Orientation on Service Sabotage Behaviour, Mediator role of ethical climate descriptive statistic, its showing the potential of each variable that able to influence dependent variable, therefore nearly all variable presenting similar potential while ethical climate mean is higher 4.207 and service sabotage Behaviour standard deviation 1.086. All variable is important for dependent variable.

Table 2

Correlation

Variable Description	Leader Human Orientation	Leader Justice Orientation	Leader Responsibility Orientation	Ethical Climate	Service Sabotage Behaviour
Leader Human	1.000	0.434	0.450	0.374	0.218

Regr

ession (Mediator role of Ethical Climate between Ethical Leader types and Service Sabotage Behaviour)

Orientation					
Leader Justice Orientation	0.434	1.000	0.575	0.163	0.270
Leader Responsibility Orientation	0.450	0.575	1.000	0.189	0.251
Ethical Climate	0.374	0.163	0.189	1.000	0.253
Service Sabotage Behaviour	0.218	0.270	0.251	0.253	1.000

Table 2 showing examines the impact of ethical leadership three types i.e., (1) Leader Human Orientation, (2) Leader Responsibility Orientation, and (3) Leader Justice Orientation on Service Sabotage Behaviour, Mediator role of ethical climate the correlation matrix applied to test the endogenous issue assessment, valued +1 and -1; which variable nearby 1 aspects endogenous issue. Thus, the result indicates no endogenous problem between any variable and all variable have positive associate with each other.

Table 3
 Regression (Service Sabotage Behaviour)

Variable	Coefficient	t-Statistic	Prob.
Leader Human Orientation	0.4449***	4.767529	0.0000
Leader Justice Orientation	0.2872***	2.817848	0.0054
Leader Responsibility Orientation	0.20225*	1.955911	0.0520
R-squared	-0.014015	Mean dependent var	3.656085
Adjusted R-squared	-0.024919	S.D. dependent var	1.088248
S.E. of regression	1.101724	Akaike info criterion	3.047375
Sum squared resid	225.7660	Schwarz criterion	3.098831
Log likelihood	-284.9769	Hannan-Quinn criter.	3.068221
Durbin-Watson stat	1.970676		

Table 3 showing Regression examines the impact of ethical leadership three types i.e., (1) Leader Human Orientation, (2) Leader Responsibility Orientation, and (3) Leader Justice Orientation on Service Sabotage Behaviour. Leader Human Orientation, Leader Responsibility Orientation, and Leader Justice Orientation are independent variable and Service Sabotage behaviour is dependent variable, the result of above table showing Leader Human Orientation 0.4449***, and Leader Responsibility Orientation 0.2872*** 1% highly significant impact on service sabotage behaviour. Meanwhile Leader Justice Orientation is * 10% significant impact on service sabotage behaviour. Result indicates Leader Human Orientation, Leader Responsibility Orientation high influence variable as compare to Leader Justice Orientation for Service Sabotage Behaviour.

Table 4

Variable	Coefficient	t-Statistic	Prob.
Ethical Climate	0.3927***	4.661172	0.0000
Leader Human Orientation	0.131350	1.181168	0.2391
Leader Justice Orientation	0.23869**	2.454027	0.0151
Leader Responsibility Orientation	0.152180	1.542277	0.1247
R-squared	0.092555	Mean dependent var	3.656085
Adjusted R-squared	0.077840	S.D. dependent var	1.088248
S.E. of regression	1.045036	Akaike info criterion	2.946916
Sum squared resid	202.0384	Schwarz criterion	3.015524
Log likelihood	-274.4836	Hannan-Quinn criter.	2.974711
Durbin-Watson stat	1.977106		

Table 4 showing Regression examines the impact of ethical leadership three types i.e., (1) Leader Human Orientation, (2) Leader Responsibility Orientation, and (3) Leader Justice Orientation on Service Sabotage Behaviour and mediator role of ethical climate. Leader Human Orientation, Leader Responsibility Orientation, and Leader Justice Orientation are independent variable, Service Sabotage behaviour is dependent variable and ethical climate is mediator. The above result indicated ethical climate 0.3929*** high significant impact on service sabotage behaviour, Meanwhile only Leader Justice Orientation is 0.23869** significant impact on service sabotage behaviour when mediator role of ethical climate, Leader Human Orientation and Leader Responsibility Orientation insignificant impact when mediator role apply between ethical leader type and service sabotage behaviour. Ethical climate highly important when direct influence on service sabotage behaviour while reduce the effect other ethical leader type.

Table 5
 Robustness Test (Service Sabotage Behaviour)

Variable	Coefficient	z-Statistic	Prob.
Leader Human Orientation	0.4619***	5.295152	0.0000
Leader Justice Orientation	0.3684***	3.866017	0.0001

Leader Responsibility Orientation	0.145277	1.503010	0.1328
Robust Statistics			
R-squared	0.058485	Adjusted R-squared	0.048361
Rw-squared	0.238975	Adjust Rw-squared	0.238975
Akaike info criterion	278.5613	Schwarz criterion	287.7100
Deviance	157.7677	Scale	0.761617
Rn-squared statistic	2601.2***Prob (Rn-squared stat.) 0.000000		
Non-robust Statistics			
Mean dependent var	3.656085	S.D. dependent var	1.088248
S.E. of regression	1.116037	Sum squared resid	231.6703

Table 5 showing examines the impact of ethical leadership three types i.e., (1) Leader Human Orientation, (2) Leader Responsibility Orientation, and (3) Leader Justice Orientation on Service Sabotage Behaviour robustness that indicate validate and sustainable results, Thus, Result of Table 5 showing Leader Human Orientation 0.4619***, and Leader Justice Orientation 0.3684*** highly significant for Service Sabotage Behaviour, while Leader Responsibility Orientation showing insignificant for service sabotage behaviour. All variable are highly important for education sector due to employee's behaviour, and for quality of work. Ethical leadership types essential emphasis on employee's behaviour to avoid service-sabotage behaviour.

CONCLUSION

The main aim of study is to assessment the effect of ethical leadership three types i.e., (1) Leader Human Orientation, (2) Leader Responsibility Orientation, and (3) Leader Justice Orientation on Service Sabotage Behaviour and mediator role of ethical climate. Study motivated with Pakistan education institute and their employee's ethical standard and service sabotage behaviour. Ethical principles not established in institution a solid reason for employee's service sabotage behaviours. In order roles of employees behaviour in education institution must regularized. The results of study also confirming ethical leadership three types i.e., (1) Leader Human Orientation, (2) Leader Responsibility Orientation, and (3) Leader Justice Orientation standard is important and leadership role enhances when it applied in education institution. Descriptive statistics indicated the

potential of each variable is high that able to influence dependent variable, while ethical climate mean 4.207 and service sabotage Behaviour standard deviation 1.086 are highest. All variable is important for dependent variable. Correlation matrix result indicated no endogenous problem between any variable and all variable have positive associate with each other. Regression result the impact of ethical leadership three types i.e., (1) Leader Human Orientation, (2) Leader Responsibility Orientation, and (3) Leader Justice Orientation on Service Sabotage Behaviour. Leader Human Orientation 0.4449***, and Leader Responsibility Orientation 0.2872*** are 1% highly significant impact on service sabotage behaviour. Meanwhile Leader Justice Orientation is * 10% significant impact on service sabotage behaviour. Result also indicates Leader Human Orientation, Leader Responsibility Orientation high influence variable as compare to Leader Justice Orientation for Service Sabotage Behaviour. Regression examines the impact of ethical leadership three types on Service Sabotage Behaviour and mediator role of ethical climate. Surprising results, indicated ethical climate 0.3929*** direct high significant impact on service sabotage behaviour, Meanwhile only Leader Justice Orientation is 0.23869** significant impact on service sabotage behaviour when mediator role of ethical climate, Leader Human Orientation and Leader Responsibility Orientation insignificant impact when mediator role apply between ethical leader type and service sabotage behaviour. Inverse influencing impact on ethical leadership types, when mediator applied Leader Justice Orientation influence role increase and Leader Human Orientation and Leader Responsibility Orientation influence role reduced. Robustness indicated all variable are highly important for education sector due to employee's behaviour, and for quality of work. Study recommended education institute Employee's behaviour highly important for institution, student, society, and quality of work maintains through employees efficient behaviour and ethical leadership types role enhance when education institution implement principles and avoid behaviour reactions, ethical leader must focus on employee's behaviour to avoid service sabotage behaviour. Educational institute more focus on ethical leader and service sabotage behaviour,

because Ethical leadership types essential and its emphasis on employee's behaviour that avoid service-sabotage behaviour.

REFERENCES

- Abubakar, A. M. and H. Arasli (2016). "Dear top management, please don't make me a cynic: intention to sabotage." Journal of Management Development **35**(10): 1266-1286.
- Altahat, S. M. and T. Atan (2018). "Role of Healthy Work Environments in Sustainability of Goal Achievement; Ethical Leadership, Intention to Sabotage and Psychological Capital in Jordanian Universities." Sustainability **10**(10): 3559.
- Arif, S. and S. Al Hassan (2022). "Impact of Psychological Contract Breach on Employees' Sabotage and Whistle-Blowing Behaviors through Perceived Organizational Frustration." Journal of Development and Social Sciences **3**(2): 1125-1138
- Ashforth, B. E. and R. H. Humphrey (1993). "Emotional labor in service roles: The influence of identity." Academy of management review **18**(1): 88-115.
- Bagan-Sebastian, J., et al. (1992). "A clinical study of 205 patients with oral lichen planus." Journal of Oral and Maxillofacial surgery **50**(2): 116-118.
- Browning, V. (2008). "An exploratory study into deviant behaviour in the service encounter: How and why front-line employees engage in deviant behaviour." Journal of Management & Organization **14**(4): 451-471.
- Carpendale, J. I. (2000). "Kohlberg and Piaget on stages and moral reasoning." Developmental Review **20**(2): 181-205.
- Corley, M. C. and P. Minick (2002). Moral distress or moral comfort. Bioethics Forum, MIDWEST BIOETHICS CENTER.
- Cropanzano, R., et al. (2003). The impact of display rules and emotional labor on psychological well-being at work. Emotional and physiological processes and positive intervention strategies, Emerald Group Publishing Limited. **3**: 45-89.
- Cull en, J. B., et al. (2003). "The effects of ethical climates on organizational commitment: A two-study analysis." Journal of business ethics **46**: 127-141.
- Diefendorff, J. M. and E. M. Richard (2003). "Antecedents and consequences of emotional display rule perceptions." Journal of applied psychology **88**(2): 284.
- Dierkes, M. and K. Zimmerman (1994). "The institutional dimension of business ethics: an agenda for reflection research and action." Journal of business ethics **13**: 533-541.
- Dimitriou, C. K. and C. H. Schwepker Jr (2019). "Enhancing the lodging experience through ethical leadership." International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management **31**(2): 669-690.
- Enwereuzor, I. K. (2023). "Dispositional greed and knowledge sabotage: the roles of cutting corners at work and ethical leadership." Current Psychology: 1-15.
- Fehr, R., et al. (2015). "Moralized leadership: The construction and consequences of ethical leader perceptions." Academy of management review **40**(2): 182-209.
- Ford, R. C. and W. D. Richardson (1994). "Ethical decision making: A review of the empirical literature." Journal of business ethics **13**: 205-22
- Giardini, A. and M. Frese (2006). "Reducing the negative effects of emotion work in service occupations: emotional competence as a psychological resource." Journal of Occupational Health Psychology **11**(1): 63.
- Gremler, D. D. and K. P. Gwinner (2000). "Customer-employee rapport in service relationships." Journal of Service Research **3**(1): 82-104.
- Harris, L. C. and E. Ogbonna (2002). "Exploring service sabotage: The antecedents, types and consequences of frontline, deviant, antiservice behaviors." Journal of Service Research **4**(3): 163-183.
- Harris, L. C. and E. Ogbonna (2006). "Service sabotage: A study of antecedents and consequences." Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science **34**: 543-558.
- Harris, L. C. and E. Ogbonna (2009). "Service sabotage: The dark side of service

- dynamics." Business horizons **52**(4): 325-335.
- Harris, L. C. and E. Ogbonna (2012). "Motives for service sabotage: an empirical study of front-line workers." The Service Industries Journal **32**(13): 2027-2046.
- Jamil, M. N. and A. Rasheed (2023). "How does Corporate Social Environment contribute to firm sustainability: mediator role of Social Capital." Journal on Innovation and Sustainability RISUS **14**(1): 77-86.
- Kurtines, W. and E. B. Greif (1974). "The development of moral thought: Review and evaluation of Kohlberg's approach." Psychological bulletin **81**(8): 453.
- Kutnick, P. (1986). "Judgment and Moral Action: Kohlberg's Theory, Criticism and Revision." Lawrence Kohlberg, Consensus and controversy **1**: 125.
- Mukhtar, Z., et al. (2022). "The Effect of Employee Diversity on Organizational Performance in Textile Industry." Journal of Policy Research **8**(3): 307-31
- Murphy, P. R., et al. (1992). "Executive attitudes, organizational size and ethical issues: Perspectives on a service industry." Journal of business ethics **11**: 11-19.
- Ogbonna, E. and L. Harris (2009). "Motives for service sabotage: An empirical study of front-line worker behaviour."
- Rahmat, A. and A. Bastian (2022). "Impact of Unscrupulous Management on Moral Identity and Knowledge Sabotage Behavior." SAINS ORGANISASI **1**(4): 270-275.
- Ramshida, A. and K. Manikandan (2013). "Organizational commitment as a mediator of counterproductive work behavior and organizational culture." International Journal of Social Science & Interdisciplinary Research **2**(2): 59-69.
- Randall, D. M. and A. M. Gibson (1990). "Methodology in business ethics research: A review and critical assessment." Journal of business ethics **9**: 457-471.
- Robertson, D. C. (1993). "Empiricism in business ethics: Suggested research directions." Journal of business ethics **12**: 585-599.
- Schneider, B. and D. E. Bowen (1992). "Personnel/human resources management in the service sector." Research in personnel and human resources management **10**(1): 1-30.
- Schneider, B. and A. E. Reichers (1983). "On the etiology of climates." Personnel psychology **36**(1): 19-39.
- Schwepker, J., Charles H, et al. (2019). "Reducing service sabotage and improving employee commitment to service quality." Journal of Services Marketing **33**(5): 615-625.
- Shao, R. and D. P. Skarlicki (2014). "Service employees' reactions to mistreatment by customers: A comparison between North America and East Asia." Personnel psychology **67**(1): 23-59.
- Shinwari, M. N., et al. (2023). "Exploring The Nexus Between Emotional Intelligent And Academic Engagement Of University Students." Journal of Positive School Psychology: 1762-1772.
- Siegel, D., et al. (1992). "Diuretics, serum and intracellular electrolyte levels, and ventricular arrhythmias in hypertensive men." Jama **267**(8): 1083-1089.
- Sinclair, A. (1993). "Approaches to organisational culture and ethics." Journal of business ethics **12**: 63-73.
- Sulu, S., et al. (2010). "Work alienation as a mediator of the relationship between organizational injustice and organizational commitment: Implications for healthcare professionals." International Journal of Business and Management **5**(8): 27.
- Taylor, L. and P. Walton (2020). Industrial sabotage: Motives and meanings. Risk Management, Routledge: 283-310.
- Tyson, T. (1992). "Does believing that everyone else is less ethical have an impact on work behavior?" Journal of business ethics **11**: 707-717.
- Viezzer, J., et al. (2018). "Climate change vulnerability analysis at the local level: lessons learnt from Brazil on how to conduct participative processes." Climate Change Adaptation in Latin America: Managing Vulnerability, Fostering Resilience: 283-298.
- Vitell, S. J. and D. L. Davis (1990). "Ethical beliefs of MIS professionals: The frequency and

- opportunity for unethical behavior." Journal of business ethics **9**: 63-70.
- Vitell, S. J. and D. L. Davis (1990). "The relationship between ethics and job satisfaction: An empirical investigation." Journal of business ethics **9**: 489-494.
- Williams, D. R. and C. Collins (1995). "US socioeconomic and racial differences in health: patterns and explanations." Annual review of sociology **21**(1): 349-386.
- Yeşiltaş, M. and M. Tuna (2018). "The effect of ethical leadership on service sabotage." The Service Industries Journal **38**(15-16): 1133-1159.
- Yousef, A. and A. Shadi (2022). "HOW ETHICAL LEADERSHIP AND INCIVILITY TOLERANCE AFFECT INTENTION TO SABOTAGE AT JORDANIAN UNIVERSITIES?" Организационная психология **12**(3): 9-26.
- Zeithaml, V. A., et al. (1996). "The behavioral consequences of service quality." Journal of marketing **60**(2): 31-46.

